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Activity–Stability Relationship in Compositionally Tuned Magnetron Co-Sputtered Bimetallic Catalysts for Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells

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ABSTRACT

In the present study, magnetron-sputtered Pt_xM_{100-x} ($M = Co, Cu, \text{ and } Y; x = 25, 50, 75, \text{ and } 100$) bimetallic alloys were investigated as PEMFC cathodes. Accurate composition and layer thickness control enabled a systematic study of the correlation between the alloy composition, its activity, and stability. The catalysts underwent thorough characterization, employing a diverse portfolio of characterization techniques such as scanning electron microscopy, energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction, and cyclic voltammetry. The activity of all investigated alloys was tested directly in a fuel cell device, whereas stability was assessed through potentiodynamic cycling in a half-cell. The activity–stability index, considering experimental results for both activity and stability, was calculated and compared for all investigated catalysts. All alloys exhibited a volcano-type trend in the activity–stability index as a function of the concentration of the alloying element with maxima observed for $Pt_{50}Co_{50}$, $Pt_{50}Cu_{50}$, and $Pt_{75}Y_{25}$ for respective alloys, surpassing that of monometallic platinum. Overall, $Pt_{50}Co_{50}$ emerged as a catalyst with the highest activity–stability ratio.

1 | Introduction

Hydrogen-powered proton exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs) stand as a promising environmentally friendly technology for a broad range of applications, ranging from powering vehicles to energy storage. However, platinum used as a catalyst in such fuel cells is expensive and scarce, and thus reducing its usage has been a key focus in research and development over the past decade [1]. This is especially valid for the PEMFC cathode where a sluggish oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) takes place, which requires a significantly higher quantity of catalyst with respect to the anode side [2]. It has been shown that one of the most

promising ways to reduce platinum usage on the cathode side is its alloying with another cheaper and more abundant metal [3]. The choice of the alloying metal as well as its quantity requires a delicate balance between catalytic activity and the binding energy (BE) of reaction intermediates according to the Sabatier principle. Only specific elements can increase the catalytic activity of platinum through precise tuning of its geometric and electronic structure [4, 5].

A wide range of Pt_xM_{100-x} alloys has been tested, including alloys of platinum with 3d transition metals, such as iron, nickel, copper, and cobalt, which demonstrated two to three times larger

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activity compared to monometallic platinum [6–8]. Alloys of Pt with other transition metals like titanium and vanadium were also examined, but their activity, although superior to platinum, was lower than in the case of the previously mentioned alloys [6]. Recently, platinum alloys with rare earth elements have become the focus of significant research interest [9–13]. For example, the Pt₇₅Y₂₅ alloy demonstrated 11 times higher activity than platinum [10]. Similar results were also obtained for Pt_xGd catalysts [11]. The further advantage of such bimetallic alloys is that the partial replacement of platinum by cheaper and more abundant elements significantly lowers the catalyst cost.

Nonetheless, such alloys often exhibit reduced stability under the hostile electrochemical environment of the PEMFC cathode, thus compromising its long-term performance. It has been shown that in the case of a binary PtM system, the faster dissolution of the less noble metal leads to their dealloying and further exacerbates the well-established platinum degradation pathways, which involve an interplay between multiple mechanisms such as dissolution of platinum, Ostwald ripening, coalescence, and carbon support corrosion [14–18].

Further optimization of the aforementioned alloys through the use of sophisticated structures such as core-shell nanoparticles [19], nanowires [20], nanodendrites [21], nanocages [22], and other intricate designs has not only further increased their activity but also significantly enhanced their stability. Specifically, the activity of Pt₃Ni nanoframes demonstrated an improvement factor of over 16 compared to commercial Pt/C electrocatalyst, and their activity loss was negligible after 10 000 potential cycles [22]. In turn, Mo-doped Pt–Ni nano-octahedra exhibited even more remarkable enhancement, achieving approximately 80- and 70-fold improvements in specific and mass activity for the ORR, respectively, and largely retaining their activity after 8000 potential cycles [23]. Nevertheless, despite these advances, scalability remains a key challenge for the widespread implementation of these alloys.

Given the challenges discussed above, it is crucial to establish a clear link between the activity and stability of such alloys. However, this presents a challenge, as comparing the activity and stability of various alloys reported in the literature is difficult. These alloys are often prepared using different methods, deposited on different substrates, and exhibit a range of structures, each with distinct morphology and composition, which may significantly influence both their activity and stability.

In this work, Pt_xM_{100–x} (M = Co, Cu, and Y; x = 25, 50, 75, and 100) model bimetallic alloy catalysts were prepared by magnetron co-sputtering, which are among the most active alloys reported in the literature [10, 24, 25]. Co-sputtering from two individual targets allowed for precise adjustment of the alloy composition by tuning the power on the magnetrons. It also enables the preparation of various bimetallic alloys with the same morphology by adjusting the time of sputtering, which determines the thickness of the deposited layer. Moreover, the morphology of magnetron-sputtered layers is characterized by randomly distributed grains with high-angle surface boundaries, serving as a suitable model for more intricate real supported nanoparticle catalysts [26, 27]. A comprehensive study involving a systematic and thorough examination that employs a diverse portfolio of characterization

techniques alongside electrochemical analyses was conducted to gain a comprehensive understanding of Pt_xM_{100–x} composition–activity–stability relationship.

2 | Experimental

Two DC magnetrons (TORUS, K. J. Lesker) with Pt (99.99%, Safina) and M targets (where M is either Co [99.95%, K. J. Lesker], Cu [99.99%, K. J. Lesker], or Y [99.99%, K. J. Lesker]) operating simultaneously were used to deposit Pt_xM_{100–x} alloys (x = 75, 50, and 25). Both targets faced the substrate at an angle of 45°. The magnetron chamber was first evacuated to a pressure of 10^{–4} Pa and then filled with an argon atmosphere at the pressure of 2.7 Pa. After cleaning the targets by sputtering outside the sample, bimetallic catalyst layers were deposited onto a nanostructured gas diffusion layer (nGDL) (Sigracet 29 BC, SGL Technologies GmbH). Sputtering time and power on both magnetrons were adjusted to obtain Pt₇₅M₂₅, Pt₅₀M₅₀, and Pt₂₅M₇₅ layers of identical 50 nm thickness. A catalyst with only pure platinum and identical thickness was also deposited as a reference sample. The deposition parameters are summarized in Table S1.

A MIRA 3 (Tescan) scanning electron microscope (SEM) was used to characterize samples' morphology. The energy of the primary electrons was set to 30 keV to ensure the highest resolution. To investigate the bulk composition of the alloys, energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) was utilized using a Bruker XFlash detector (Bruker) attached to the SEM. The energy of primary electrons during EDX measurements was then set to 5 keV for Pt–Y and 20 keV for all other alloys. EDX spectra were analyzed using Esprit 1.9 software (Bruker).

The surface composition of the samples was determined by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) using an EnviroESCA (SPECS Surface Nano Analysis GmbH) with a PHOIBOS hemispherical electron analyzer and a monochromatic Al K α X-ray source (1486.6 eV) in UHV (10^{–9} mbar) conditions. The size of the irradiated area was approximately 200 μ m. The Pt 4f, Co 2p, Cu 2p, and Y 3d spectra were collected and analyzed using KolXP software (Kolibrick.net).

X-ray diffraction (XRD) was used to measure the crystallographic structure of the investigated samples. The XRD measurements were performed using a SmartLab diffractometer (Rigaku) equipped with a 9 kW rotating anode x-ray source (Cu K α radiation, λ = 0.15418 nm), a parabolic multilayer mirror in the primary beam, a set of axial divergence eliminating Soller slits with an acceptance of 5° in both incident and diffracted beams, and a HighPix-3000 2D hybrid pixel single-photon counting detector. The measurements were done in the parallel beam glancing angle XRD geometry (GAXRD) with a parallel beam Soller slit collimator (0.5° acceptance) in the diffracted beam. The constant angle of the incidence beam of 0.6° was used for the measurements.

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) was conducted in a half-cell configuration inside an electrochemical cell filled with N₂-saturated 0.1 M HClO₄ solution. A three-electrode setup containing the investigated catalyst deposited onto glassy carbon (Pine Research, 5 mm diameter, 0.196 cm² surface area) as a working electrode (WE),

a platinum wire (99.99%, Pine Research) as a counter electrode (CE), and leak-free Ag/AgCl in saturated KCl (Monokrystaly s.r.o.) as a reference electrode (RE) was used. Potential sweeping at 200 mV s^{-1} within $0-1 V_{\text{RHE}}$ potential range was performed using an SP-150 potentiostat (Bio-Logic). The measured potentials were then converted to the reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) scale. For screening the durability, the investigated catalysts were deposited on a $5 \text{ mm} \times 10 \text{ mm}$ piece of nGDL, with half of it submerged into the electrolyte and used as a WE. The samples were subjected to 1000 potentiodynamic linear cycles from 0 to $1 V_{\text{RHE}}$.

To test the performance of the catalyst, nGDL with the deposited catalyst layer was used as a cathode in a fuel cell, whereas a commercial catalyst with 0.3 mg cm^{-2} 40% platinum on Vulcan—Carbon Paper Electrode was used as an anode. A Nafion membrane (Nafion NR-212, thickness $50.8 \mu\text{m}$, FuelCellStore) was used as an electrolyte. The fuel cell was tested using a pneumatically compressed (8 bars) graphite single cell with an active area of 4 cm^2 in a Greenlight TP-5 Research Cell test station. Measurements were performed at 70°C with fully humidified H_2 and O_2 (AirLiquide, 99.999%) gases introduced to the anode and cathode, respectively. I–P and I–V curves of the cell were measured while the current was increased linearly.

3 | Results and Discussions

3.1 | Characterization of As-Deposited $\text{Pt}_x\text{M}_{100-x}$ Catalysts

SEM images of the as-deposited Pt–M catalysts with different compositions ($\text{Pt}_{75}\text{M}_{25}$, $\text{Pt}_{50}\text{M}_{50}$, and $\text{Pt}_{25}\text{M}_{75}$; M = Co, Cu, and Y) deposited onto the GDL support precoated with a microporous layer composed of carbon particles of average size 50 nm are shown in Figure 1. It can be observed that all catalysts-coated carbon particles exhibit homogeneously distributed grains with average lateral sizes of approximately 10 nm . Considering the fact that the thickness of the deposited catalyst is 50 nm , we can assume a columnar nanostructure for the catalyst film, which is typical for magnetron-sputtered layers. Overall, it can be asserted that alloy morphology is independent of its composition and type, thus avoiding its potential influence on the comparison of the catalytic activity of the investigated catalysts.

The bulk composition of the as-deposited alloys was quantified from the EDX spectra shown in Figure 2 by integrating the Co $\text{K}_{\alpha 1}$ (6.930 keV), Cu $\text{K}_{\alpha 1}$ (8.047 keV), and Pt $\text{L}_{\alpha 1}$ (9442 keV) lines for Pt–Co and Pt–Cu alloys, as well as the Y $\text{L}_{\alpha 1}$ (1.923 keV) and Pt $\text{M}_{\alpha 1}$ (2.051 keV) for Pt–Y alloys. The results are summarized in Table 1. Overall, the measured compositions were akin to anticipated ones with only negligible deviations.

The samples were then analyzed using a more surface-sensitive XPS technique. Figure 3a,b shows the high-resolution Pt 4f and Co 2p XPS spectra, respectively, acquired for Pt–Co catalysts with different compositions including monometallic Pt. All Pt 4f spectra contain a single doublet at the BE value around $71.1/74.4 \text{ eV}$, which corresponds to metallic platinum contribution [28]. A more in-depth examination of the measured spectra

enables one to distinguish a composition-dependent BE shift of the corresponding core levels. Specifically, with increasing Co concentration in the alloy, the Pt 4f peak progressively shifts to higher BEs with respect to monometallic Pt, reaching approximately $71.17/74.47$, $71.25/74.55$, and $71.3/74.6 \text{ eV}$ for $\text{Pt}_{75}\text{Co}_{25}$, $\text{Pt}_{50}\text{Co}_{50}$, and $\text{Pt}_{25}\text{Co}_{75}$, respectively. The magnitude of the shift aligns well with previous experimental and theoretical studies, where, for example, an upshift of approximately 0.2 eV in the Pt 4f core levels was observed for $\text{Pt}_{50}\text{Co}_{50}$. [28–30]. Considering the identical support and the consistent morphology of the deposited catalysts, we do not expect any differences in the BE shifts due to interactions with the support and/or size effects. Therefore, such shifts are an indication of alloy formation and corresponding modification of Pt electronic structure manifested in a charge transfer due to orbital overlap. In contrast to platinum, cobalt was found to be partially oxidized, as evidenced by the Co 2p XPS spectra in Figure 3b, which complicates the observation of the anticipated shift. The position of the most intense doublet at $780.3/795.3 \text{ eV}$ could be assigned to oxidized cobalt, whereas the smaller shoulder at about $778.4/793.4 \text{ eV}$ is consistent with its metallic contribution [31]. This is apparently attributed to the formation of surface oxide layers during sample transfer through air due to the relatively high affinity of cobalt to oxygen [32]. Indeed, cobalt is known to spontaneously form, in a matter of seconds, an oxide passivation layer with approximately $0.8-1 \text{ nm}$ thickness, given by the relatively low Gibbs free energy of CoO formation ($-213.4 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) [32, 33].

Figure 3c,d displays the Pt 4f and the Cu 2p spectra of Pt–Cu alloys, respectively. Same as for the Pt–Co samples, the Pt 4f XPS spectra for all alloys contain exclusively metallic contribution. However, in contrast to the Pt–Co alloys, a noticeable shift of the Pt 4f doublet towards lower BEs was observed as the Cu concentration increased. The Pt 4f position was estimated to be at $71.0/74.3$ for $\text{Pt}_{75}\text{Cu}_{25}$, $70.8/74.1$ for $\text{Pt}_{50}\text{Cu}_{50}$, and $70.6/73.9$ for $\text{Pt}_{25}\text{Cu}_{75}$ alloys. This is consistent with findings in the literature, where Pt 4f core levels were observed to shift to lower binding energies upon alloying Pt with Cu [34, 35]. Core-level shifts are typically associated with changes in the valence state due to the hybridization between neighboring atoms during alloying. Lee et al., through XPS and XANES studies, proposed that the opposite core-level shifts observed in Pt–Co and Pt–Cu alloys are primarily driven by their different alterations in the d-valence electrons, specifically in the 5d orbital [36]. In the Cu 2p spectra, a prominent doublet at about $932/951.2 \text{ eV}$ was detected together with a less intense doublet at approximately $934/953.8 \text{ eV}$. The former peak can be attributed to metallic Cu, whereas the latter corresponds to its oxidized state [37]. In contrast to Co in the Pt–Co alloys, the intensity of peaks corresponding to oxidized copper in the Pt–Cu alloys is significantly smaller than the metallic contribution. This discrepancy can be explained by the lower affinity of copper to oxygen, attributed to the lower Gibbs free energy of CuO and Cu_2O formation of -128.3 and $-147.9 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, respectively [35]. Indeed, the formation of only 0.13 nm thick oxide passivation layer was shown to spontaneously form within the first 4 min of copper exposure to dry air [38]. The well-defined metallic peak enables estimation of the corresponding shift in Cu 2p core levels resulting from alloying with Pt. The upshift of Cu 2p core level from 932.02 eV for $\text{Pt}_{75}\text{Cu}_{25}$ to 932.06 eV for $\text{Pt}_{25}\text{Cu}_{75}$ alloy further confirms the formation of the Pt–Cu alloy [36].

FIGURE 1 | SEM images of nGDL with 50 nm sputtered layer of Pt–Co (upper row), Pt–Cu (middle row), and Pt–Y (bottom row) alloy catalysts.

FIGURE 2 | EDX spectra of as-deposited (a) Pt–Co, (b) Pt–Cu, and (c) Pt–Y alloy catalysts normalized to intensity of the corresponding platinum peak.

TABLE 1 | Relative atomic concentrations of M (M = Co, Cu, and Y) in the sputtered Pt_xM_{100-x} alloy catalysts.

	$Pt_{75}Co_{25}$	$Pt_{50}Co_{50}$	$Pt_{25}Co_{75}$	$Pt_{75}Cu_{25}$	$Pt_{50}Cu_{50}$	$Pt_{25}Cu_{75}$	$Pt_{75}Y_{25}$	$Pt_{50}Y_{50}$	$Pt_{25}Y_{75}$
M (at%) (EDX)	25	51	73	28	44	73	23	53	74
M (at%) (XPS)	30	58	76	22	47	73	27	68	88

Finally, the Pt 4f and Y 3d core-level regions of the Pt–Y alloys are shown in Figure 3e,f, respectively. Similar to all previously described alloys, Pt was present in the metallic state. Pt 4f peaks were slightly shifted to lower BEs as Y concentration in the alloys increased. The Pt 4f position was estimated to be at

approximately 71.05/74.35 for $Pt_{75}Y_{25}$, 70.95/74.25 for $Pt_{50}Y_{50}$, and 70.85/74.15 for $Pt_{25}Y_{75}$ alloys. This shift is consistent with previous reports, primarily focused on Pt₃Y alloys, where a similar trend in negative BE shifts for Pt 4f core levels was observed [39–41]. In turn, the Y 3d spectra appeared to be mostly oxidized,

FIGURE 3 | (a) XPS Pt 4f spectra and (b) XPS Co 2p spectra of as-deposited monometallic Pt and Pt–Co alloy catalysts; (c) XPS Pt 4f spectra and (d) XPS Cu 2p spectra of as-deposited monometallic Pt and Pt–Cu alloy catalysts; (e) XPS Pt 4f spectra and (f) XPS Y 3d spectra of as-deposited monometallic Pt and Pt–Y alloy catalysts.

containing one doublet at 156.8/158.8 eV, corresponding to Y_2O_3 , and the second doublet at 157.7/159.7 eV, which can be assigned to $Y_2(CO_3)_3$ as well as yttrium hydrates or hydroxides [39, 40]. Only a minor contribution of metallic Y was detected at approximately 156.1/158.1 eV [10]. This complicates the observation of the corresponding shift of Y 3d core levels as a result of alloying. The predominantly oxidized yttrium in the case of the Pt_3Y alloy was observed elsewhere and is associated with surface yttrium atoms reacting with oxygen during the sample transfer through the air [10]. Compared to previous alloying metals, yttrium exhibits the highest tendency to oxidize. The Gibbs free energy of Y_2O_3 formation is $-1800 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, which is significantly lower than that of the cobalt and copper oxides discussed above [33]. It was demonstrated that yttrium forms a passivation oxide layer of almost 10 nm thickness on its surface within the first 2 h of exposure to air [42], which explains the minor contribution of metallic yttrium observed on Y 3d XPS spectra.

The presented findings from XPS results confirm the overall modification of the Pt electronic structure resulting from its alloying with cobalt, copper, and yttrium. Drawing on extensive prior research, the core level shift is a good indicator of the shift in d-band center relative to the Fermi level [43], which is a key parameter that determines the ORR kinetics through the favorable alterations of the BE of reaction intermediates (O, OH) with catalyst surface [5, 44].

The XPS spectra were also analyzed to calculate the relative elemental atomic composition of all investigated alloys. The results, considering sensitivity factors, are summarized in Table 1. It can be observed that, although overall these values are comparable to those obtained using EDX, they are slightly higher for Pt–Co and Pt–Y alloys. This difference may arise from a slight segregation of Co and Y from the subsurface region to the surface of the respective alloy during its oxidation in air, which is discerned by XPS [45, 46]. In the case of Pt–Cu catalysts, calculated from the corresponding XPS spectra (considering the overlap of Pt 4f states with Cu 3p [37]), there was no discernible tendency for a higher concentration of copper when comparing XPS results with EDX due to lower Pt–Cu surface oxidation, and overall, these values are very similar to those obtained using EDX. It is worth noting that the presence of these oxides on the surface of the alloy catalysts is not anticipated to impact activity measurements, as these oxides should readily dissolve under corrosive conditions of a fuel cell cathode, resulting in the formation of Pt-terminated alloy structures.

The crystallographic structure of sputtered alloys was further investigated with XRD. The XRD patterns obtained from the analyzed layers are shown in Figure 4. The diffractograms for the Pt–Co and Pt–Cu catalysts in Figure 4a,b showed continuous shift of the diffraction peaks toward higher angles, compared to pure Pt, as the concentration of Co and Cu in the alloy increased, in accordance with Vegard's law. This shift corresponds to the emergence of compressive strain, induced by the smaller atomic radii of Co and Cu, which is beneficial for ORR [5]. Indeed, the lattice constant computed from the corresponding patterns changed from 3.922 Å for monometallic Pt to 3.867, 3.812, and 3.684 Å for $Pt_{75}Co_{25}$, $Pt_{50}Co_{50}$, and $Pt_{25}Co_{75}$, respectively, and to 3.862, 3.796, and 3.713 Å for $Pt_{75}Cu_{25}$, $Pt_{50}Cu_{50}$, and $Pt_{25}Cu_{75}$, respectively. The above results are in line with previously reported findings [47,

48]. The diffraction peaks for the Pt–Y layers in Figure 4c are noticeably broader than those observed for the other alloys, which is consistent with what has been reported for Pt_3Y alloys in the literature, where the relatively broad diffraction peaks in Pt–Y were attributed to the very small size of coherently diffracting domains and the presence of microstrains [40, 49]. Additionally, unlike other alloys, Pt–Y did not follow Vegard's law. Although no noticeable shift in the diffractogram was observed for the $Pt_{75}Y_{25}$ layer compared to pure Pt in Figure 4c, the calculated lattice parameter was 3.899 Å, which is slightly lower than that of pure Pt (3.922 Å). Despite the larger atomic radius of Y, a contraction of the Pt lattice has been previously observed for the Pt_3Y alloy [49, 50]. This seemingly counterintuitive behavior has been explained through a high electron affinity of Pt that affects the electronic density of Y and leads to a decrease in the radius of the Y atom along with the depletion of electrons [50]. Indeed, the XPS results in Figure 3e support this explanation, showing a negative shift in the Pt core levels. For other compositions with higher Y content, a slight shift toward lower angles was eventually observed, suggesting the emergence of tensile strain. The refined lattice parameters for $Pt_{50}Y_{50}$ and $Pt_{25}Y_{75}$ layers were 3.992 and 3.998 Å, respectively. The changes in the lattice constant were smaller than anticipated and predicted by Vegard's law, likely due to alterations in the electronic density of Y induced by alloying with Pt [50]. It is important to highlight that for the $Pt_{25}Y_{75}$ layer containing the highest Y amount, an additional peak around 30° was observed, corresponding to pure Y [49]. This suggests the presence of Y-rich phases in the sample, likely related to the high concentration of Y-oxides observed in the XPS spectra (Figure 3f).

The identical catalyst layers were then deposited onto glassy carbon substrates for electrochemical investigation in a half-cell configuration. Figure 5 depicts cyclic voltammograms recorded over all investigated samples in N_2 purged 0.1 M $HClO_4$ solution at a 200 mV s^{-1} scan rate. All CV curves comprise the hydrogen oxidation/reduction, or the so-called H_{UPD} region ($0-0.3 V_{RHE}$), and platinum oxidation/reduction regions ($0.6-1.0 V_{RHE}$), separated by a double-layer potential region ($0.3-0.6 V_{RHE}$) typical for polycrystalline platinum. Only CVs of the Pt–Cu alloys contain additional peaks corresponding to the Cu oxidation/reduction [51]. It can be seen that with increasing M concentration, all currents decrease, which is attributed to the lower concentration of Pt in the alloy. In general, the Pt–Y alloys displayed higher currents, particularly in the H_{UPD} region, which is directly linked to the surface area of Pt, followed by Pt–Co and Pt–Cu alloys. This behavior could be attributed to the initially larger amount of oxides present in the Pt–Y alloys as was evidenced in XPS spectra, which upon dissolution form a so-called Pt skeleton structure on the alloy surface, with increased surface area [52].

3.2 | Assessing the Activity and Stability of Pt_xM_{100-x} Catalysts

After thorough characterization, all samples were tested as cathodes in a fuel cell device. A total of three independent measurements were conducted for each composition to ensure statistically accurate data. The selected (median) polarization curves, along with the power density characteristics of a single cell containing Pt_xM_{100-x} and monometallic Pt cathode catalysts prepared by magnetron sputtering, are presented in Figure 6.

FIGURE 4 | XRD diffractograms of as-deposited (a) Pt-Co, (b) Pt-Cu, and (c) Pt-Y alloy catalysts.

FIGURE 5 | Cyclic voltammograms of (a) Pt-Co, (b) Pt-Cu, and (c) Pt-Y alloy catalysts, acquired in deaerated 0.1 M HClO₄ solution at 200 mV s⁻¹ scan rate.

FIGURE 6 | Dependence of power density (right axis) and voltage (left axis) on current density in fuel cells with (a) Pt-Co, (b) Pt-Cu, and (c) Pt-Y cathode catalysts.

The average maximum power densities (P_{av}) extracted from the corresponding curves for all investigated catalysts are summarized in Table 2, along with the platinum loading. Overall, the measured power densities were lower compared to those typically observed for chemically synthesized powder catalysts, primarily due to the relatively lower Pt loadings in sputtered samples. However, the results are consistent with previous measurements for low-loading catalysts deposited by magnetron sputtering. For

instance, a power density of 0.32 W cm⁻² was reported by Lai et al. for a Pt catalyst prepared by RF magnetron sputter deposition with a loading of 0.1 mg cm⁻² [53]. Gruber et al., using a similar technique, reported 0.203 W cm⁻² for a Pt layer with 50 nm thickness corresponding to 0.107 mg cm⁻² Pt loading [54]. The slight differences in power densities despite similar loadings could be attributed to variations in deposition parameters, the choice of support material, membranes used, etc. This is why

TABLE 2 | Average of maximum power densities (P_{av}) measured for sputtered bimetallic catalysts in fuel cell together with platinum loading (m_{Pt}) calculated for all deposited catalytic layers.

	Pt	Pt ₇₅ Co ₂₅	Pt ₅₀ Co ₅₀	Pt ₂₅ Co ₇₅	Pt ₇₅ Cu ₂₅	Pt ₅₀ Cu ₅₀	Pt ₂₅ Cu ₇₅	Pt ₇₅ Y ₂₅	Pt ₅₀ Y ₅₀	Pt ₂₅ Y ₇₅
P_{av} (W cm ⁻²)	0.39 ± 0.03	0.35 ± 0.02	0.35 ± 0.03	0.19 ± 0.02	0.36 ± 0.02	0.30 ± 0.03	0.12 ± 0.02	0.34 ± 0.03	0.27 ± 0.04	0.15 ± 0.02
m_{Pt} (mg cm ⁻²)	0.11 ± 0.01	0.083 ± 0.008	0.057 ± 0.006	0.034 ± 0.003	0.080 ± 0.008	0.063 ± 0.006	0.033 ± 0.003	0.077 ± 0.008	0.041 ± 0.004	0.019 ± 0.002

our study emphasizes maintaining consistent variables across all experiments to ensure meaningful comparisons. The power densities for bimetallic alloys in general were smaller than that of monometallic Pt and decreased with increasing concentration of metal M, which is given by the lower amount of platinum in the catalyst layer (see Table 2). Indeed, a power density of approximately 0.13 W cm⁻² was previously observed for magnetron co-sputtered Pt₅₀Co₅₀ catalyst with a thickness of 50 nm and Pt loading as low as 0.05 mg cm⁻² [55]. In our previous study, we measured power densities of 0.24, 0.2, and 0.15 W cm⁻² for Pt₇₅Ni₂₅, Pt₅₀Ni₅₀, and Pt₂₅Ni₇₅, respectively [56].

It can be seen that the overall power density depends on the platinum loading. The so-called specific power (SP) was thus calculated, representing the power per milligram of platinum [54, 56]. A detailed description of the platinum loading calculations for each sample is provided in the Supporting Information file. The SP evolution as a function of alloy type and its composition is shown in Figure 8a. In general, the SP increased linearly with the growing amount of alloying metal for all alloys up to the Pt₅₀M₅₀ composition. The most substantial increase was observed for the Pt–Co alloys, which reached an almost 50% increase in activity compared to monometallic Pt, followed by the Pt–Y alloys with a 35% increase. The Pt–Cu alloys exhibited the lowest increase in SP, reaching a 23% increase in activity compared to monometallic Pt. In turn, for the Pt₂₅M₇₅ alloys, distinct behavior was observed for different metals. Activities of Pt₂₅Co₇₅ and Pt₂₅Cu₇₅ were lower than those of Pt₅₀Co₅₀ and Pt₅₀Cu₅₀. The aforementioned volcano behavior in activity, depending on the composition of Pt–Cu and Pt–Co alloys, was previously reported for model Pt–Cu subsurface alloys with different compositions [24]. In contrast, the activity of the Pt–Y alloy did not exhibit a volcano behavior, with the Pt₂₅Y₇₅ alloy achieving higher specific activity than any other sample.

All investigated catalysts were then subjected to the degradation test consisting of 1000 potentiodynamic cycles from 0.05 to 1 V_{RHE}. SEM images of Pt–M catalysts captured before and after degradation tests are summarized in Figure 7. Overall, for the Pt₇₅M₂₅ type of catalysts, no significant morphological changes were observed. Changes in morphology, manifested by the appearance of cracks resulting from the dissolution of metal M from alloys together with a slight agglomeration of catalyst grains given by the combination of coalescence and Ostwald ripening [16], began to occur for all alloys when the concentration of the alloying element reached 50%. Such behavior was observed and described in detail for bimetallic alloys including those prepared by magnetron sputtering [16, 17, 51, 57, 58]. Further increase of the concentration of metal M in the alloy exacerbates the degradation. The Pt₂₅M₇₅ alloy type exhibited drastic morphological changes. This is because when the proportion of the less stable metal in the alloy exceeds 50%–60%, it crosses the so-called parting limit threshold, causing the alloying element to dissolve from the bulk and leads to higher dissolution rates [56, 58]. A more in-depth examination of the SEM images allowed us to conclude that among all investigated bimetallic catalysts, the Pt–Y alloys are most prone to degradation, followed by Pt–Co and Pt–Cu alloys.

In order to quantitatively assess the extent of the degradation, EDX measurements were conducted after the degradation test, and the composition extracted from these postdegradation measurements was compared with that obtained before the test

FIGURE 7 | SEM images of Pt-M catalysts deposited on nGDL before and after degradation test. The scale applies to all images.

FIGURE 8 | Dependence of (a) specific power, (b) stability index, and (c) activity–stability index on concentration of nonplatinum metal M.

(Table 1). The so-called stability index (X) was then calculated using the following equation, which represents a numerical representation of the change in composition:

$$X = (1 + c_{M2} - c_{M1}) \quad (1)$$

where c_{M1} and c_{M2} denote concentrations of metal M before and after potential cycling, respectively. In this context, a larger numerical value of the degradation coefficient corresponds to a smaller change in concentration caused by the degradation test, and a value of one corresponds to monometallic Pt, indicating no change in composition.

The resulting degradation coefficients for all investigated alloys are graphically represented in Figure 8b. The results revealed a linear decrease in stability with the increasing concentration of the alloying element for all investigated alloys. The most significant decrease was observed for Pt–Y catalysts, whereas Pt–Cu catalysts exhibited the highest stability, aligning well with the SEM observations. It is also important to note that the degradation coefficient exclusively accounts for the dealloying mechanism and does not encompass other factors, such as catalyst coarsening due to Ostwald ripening and coalescence. Nevertheless, taking into account our previous works, it can serve as an indicative measure reflecting the general trend of bimetallic catalyst degradation [16, 17, 51].

Finally, to analyze which type of alloy and composition is best in terms of the activity–stability tradeoff, the activity–stability index K was defined as follows:

$$K = \frac{P_{sp}}{P_{spPt}} (1 + c_{M2} - c_{M1}). \quad (2)$$

The computed values are plotted in Figure 8c alongside the K value for monometallic Pt, which is equal to one. All alloys exhibit a volcano trend with a peak at a certain composition. Particularly, Pt–Co and Pt–Cu alloys showed a peak at the $Pt_{50}M_{50}$ composition, whereas Pt–Y alloys demonstrated a peak at $Pt_{75}Y_{25}$. Overall, all $Pt_{75}M_{25}$ alloys exhibited superior performance compared to monometallic platinum in terms of the activity–stability ratio. Notably, $Pt_{50}Co_{50}$ emerged as a catalyst with the highest activity and moderate stability. On the other hand, the high activity of $Pt_{25}M_{75}$ catalysts was outweighed by their low stability.

4 | Conclusions

Pt_xM_{100-x} ($M = Co, Cu, \text{ and } Y; x = 25, 50, 75, \text{ and } 100$) bimetallic alloy catalysts were prepared by magnetron co-sputtering. This method allowed for the precise tuning of alloy elemental composition and morphology, enabling a systematic study of the correlation between alloy composition, activity, and stability. The composition of the deposited layers was verified by EDX and XPS measurements, whereas their morphology was examined by SEM. The alloy nature of magnetron-sputtered layers was confirmed by observing the shift in XPS Pt 4f spectra and XRD diffractograms. CV revealed increased currents in the H_{UPD} (active Pt surface area) region for Pt–Y alloys, followed by Pt–Co and Pt–Cu alloys. This observation was associated with the removal of surface oxides in the electrochemical environment.

All alloy catalysts were tested as cathodes in PEMFCs and compared with PEMFCs containing a monometallic Pt cathode catalyst. For Pt–Co and Pt–Cu catalysts, increasing the concentration of nonplatinum metal M in the alloy up to 50% led to an increase in SP, whereas the activity of catalysts with $Pt_{25}M_{75}$ composition was found to be lower. Specifically, $Pt_{50}Co_{50}$ showed the highest activity, being 90% higher than that of monometallic Pt. Similarly, $Pt_{50}Cu_{50}$ exhibited an activity 30% higher than that of Pt. Among Pt–Y catalysts, the trend of increasing SP with increasing concentration of Y continued even up to $Pt_{25}Y_{75}$ which showed 150% higher activity than that of Pt.

On the other hand, a linear decrease in stability with increasing concentration of metal M was observed for all investigated alloys during the potentiodynamic cycling to 1 V_{RHE} upper potential. Degradation was found to be most severe for Pt–Y catalysts, whereas Pt–Cu catalysts were the least affected.

Finally, the activity–stability index, considering experimental results for both the activity and stability, was calculated for all investigated catalysts. In terms of the activity–stability ratio, all alloys showed a volcano-type trend with a peak at $Pt_{50}Co_{50}$, $Pt_{50}Cu_{50}$, and $Pt_{75}Y_{25}$ for respective alloys. Notably, $Pt_{50}Co_{50}$ emerged as a catalyst with the highest activity–stability ratio.

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Data Availability Statement

The data presented in this study are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10947887>.

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Supporting Information

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